

Introduction

This document reports the answers obtained from Gemini and ChatGPT to the request for financial advice for three fake investor profiles. Before doing that, both systems were queried on what information they needed to give such advice; their answers to this preliminary question are reported in the following sections.

The other three sections contain Gemini and ChatGPT's financial advice for the three investors and an assessment of their degree of explainability and compliance with the EU MiFID directive.

Requested financial information

Question

What information do you need to give me personalized financial advice?

Gemini's Answer

While I can't provide personalized financial advice, I can tell you what information a financial advisor would typically need to give you sound financial guidance:

Financial Situation:

- **Income:** Salary, bonuses, any other forms of regular income.
- **Assets:** Savings accounts, investment accounts, retirement accounts, real estate, any valuable possessions.
- **Debts:** Mortgages, student loans, credit card debt, any other outstanding loans.
- **Net Worth:** Total assets minus total liabilities.

Financial Goals:

- **Short-term goals:** Saving for a down payment, building an emergency fund, paying off debt.
- **Long-term goals:** Retirement planning, college savings for children, funding a dream vacation.
- **Risk tolerance:** How comfortable are you with potential investment losses?

Risk Tolerance:

- This helps determine the appropriate asset allocation for your investments.
- Are you conservative, moderate, or aggressive in your risk tolerance?

Investment Time Horizon:

- When will you need access to your invested funds? Short-term goals require different investment strategies than long-term goals like retirement.

Additional Information:

- **Tax filing status:** Married, single, head of household, etc.
- **Dependents:** Do you have any children or other dependents?
- **Existing investment accounts:** If you have any, details on their holdings and performance.
- **Employer benefits:** Details on your retirement plan, health insurance, and other benefits offered by your employer.

By providing a financial advisor with this information, they can create a personalized financial plan that considers your unique circumstances and goals.

Here are some additional points to remember:

- **There is no one-size-fits-all approach to financial planning.** What works for one person might not be suitable for another.
- **Financial advisors are there to guide you, but ultimately the financial decisions are yours.**
- **It's important to feel comfortable with your financial advisor and their recommendations.**

If you're looking for personalized financial advice, consider consulting with a qualified financial advisor. They can help you develop a plan to achieve your financial goals.

ChatGPT's Answer

To provide personalized financial advice, several key pieces of information are typically required. These include:

1. **Financial Goals:** What are your short-term and long-term financial objectives? These could include saving for retirement, buying a house, funding education, starting a business, etc.
2. **Income:** Your current income level, including any additional sources of income such as investments, rental properties, or side hustles.
3. **Expenses:** A breakdown of your monthly expenses, including necessities such as housing, utilities, groceries, transportation, insurance, debt payments, entertainment, etc.
4. **Assets:** Details about your current assets, including savings accounts, investment accounts, retirement accounts, real estate, vehicles, valuable possessions, etc.
5. **Liabilities:** Any outstanding debts such as mortgages, student loans, car loans, credit card balances, personal loans, etc.
6. **Risk Tolerance:** Your willingness and ability to tolerate fluctuations in the value of your investments. This helps determine an appropriate investment strategy.

7. **Time Horizon:** The length of time you plan to hold investments before needing to access the funds. This affects your investment choices and risk tolerance.
8. **Tax Situation:** Information about your tax filing status, current tax rate, and any significant tax considerations that may impact your financial decisions.
9. **Legal and Estate Planning:** Details about any existing wills, trusts, or other estate planning documents, as well as any legal considerations that may affect your financial situation.
10. **Other Considerations:** Any other relevant information such as health concerns, family situations, or unique financial circumstances that may impact your financial planning.

With this information, a financial advisor can analyze your current financial situation, assess your goals and risk tolerance, and develop a personalized financial plan to help you achieve your objectives. Keep in mind that personalized financial advice should be tailored to your specific circumstances and should be reviewed regularly to account for any changes in your situation or financial goals.

Personas and recommendations

Low-Risk Investor Persona

Description

I am Bailey, 25 years-old, just starting in the workforce with a salary of \$30,000. However, I have \$10,000 in savings and no dependents, but monthly student loan of \$1000. I have a keen interest in low-risk sustainable and ethical investing, looking for a investment advice that aligns with their values.

Gemini's Answer

Hi Bailey! That's a great starting point. Here's some advice on low-risk sustainable and ethical investing with your current situation:

Considering Your Situation:

- **Starting Out:** You're new to the workforce, so focus on building a solid financial foundation.
- **Student Loans:** \$1000 monthly payment is a significant chunk of your income. Prioritize paying them down while you invest.
- **Savings:** You have a good head start with \$10,000 in savings.

Investing for You:

- **Low-Risk Approach:** Since you're new to investing and have student loans, a low-risk approach is wise. This might involve a longer investment time horizon (since you're young).
- **Sustainable and Ethical Investing:** Great! There are several options that align with your values.

Here's how you can get started:

1. **Emergency Fund:** Aim for 3-6 months of living expenses in a high-yield savings account. This provides a safety net for unexpected costs. With a \$30,000 salary, aim for \$9,000 - \$18,000 before aggressively investing.
2. **Pay Down Student Loans:** While building your emergency fund, consider putting extra money towards your student loans. Reducing your debt will free up more income for future investing.
3. **Start Small and Invest Regularly:** Once you have your emergency fund in place, even with the student loans, you can start investing. A low monthly contribution (even \$50-\$100) adds up over time, especially with the power of compound interest.
4. **Choose Sustainable/Ethical Investment Options:** Here are some options that fit your criteria:
 - **Robo-advisors with a sustainable focus:** These automated investment platforms consider ESG factors and allow for small initial investments.
 - **Sustainable mutual funds or ETFs:** These invest in a basket of companies that meet ESG criteria and offer diversification with a lower risk profile. Look for low expense ratio funds.
 - **Fractional Shares:** Some platforms allow buying fractions of shares, letting you invest in companies you believe in even with a limited budget.

Remember:

- **Do your research:** Before investing in any specific fund or company, research their ESG practices and investment strategy.
- **Start Conservative:** With student loans, prioritize a lower-risk approach until your debt is under control. Gradually increase your investment amount as your income grows.
- **Consider a Financial Advisor:** A fee-based financial advisor specializing in sustainable investing can provide personalized guidance based on your complete financial picture.

By taking these steps, you can start investing sustainably and ethically while managing your student loans and building a secure financial future. Remember, consistency is key! Even small contributions regularly can lead to significant returns over the long term.

Explanatory Questions and Assessment

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<i>What information was used to assess the client's knowledge and experience in the investment field, financial situation, investment objectives, and risk tolerance?</i>	Answered (i.e., by first asking the system what information it needed to be able to provide personalised investment advice).
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<i>How does the recommended investment strategy meet the client's investment objectives, considering their personal circumstances, investment term required, knowledge and experience, attitude to risk, capacity to sustain losses and sustainability preferences?</i>	Partly answered (i.e., the actual knowledge and experience of the client are not taken into account, but besides this, the question is answered).
<i>What measures were taken, post-hoc, to ensure that the advice given meets the client's investment objectives, financial capacity for investment risks, and knowledge understanding of the risks?</i>	This was not answered. The tool was not provided by an investment firm. It was mainly designed to return a generic 'investment strategy' rather than personalised investment advice.
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<i>Is the information provided to the client fair, clear, and not misleading?</i>	Not answered as such by the system, but the explanations appear to be fair, clear, and accurate. Yet, we can only conclude that the system provided relevant information, and not conclude whether the information is adequate/true or not.

ChatGPT's Answer

Thank you for providing that information, Bailey. Given your situation and interests, here are some personalized investment advice and considerations:

1. **Emergency Fund:** It's great that you have \$10,000 in savings. Before considering investing, ensure you have an emergency fund covering at least three to six months of living expenses. This fund should be easily accessible in case of unexpected expenses or emergencies.
2. **Debt Management:** With a monthly student loan payment of \$1000, it's important to prioritize debt repayment. Consider making extra payments towards your student loans to reduce the principal amount and decrease the overall interest paid over time.
3. **Investment Strategy:** Since you're interested in low-risk sustainable and ethical investing, you may want to consider socially responsible investing (SRI) or environmental, social, and governance (ESG) investing. These approaches consider environmental, social, and ethical criteria alongside financial returns.
4. **Diversification:** Diversifying your investments across different asset classes such as stocks, bonds, and possibly real estate can help reduce risk. Look for sustainable and ethical investment funds or ETFs that align with your values.
5. **Robo-Advisors:** Consider using a robo-advisor platform that offers socially responsible investment options. These platforms use algorithms to create and manage investment portfolios based on your risk tolerance, financial goals, and values.
6. **Research and Due Diligence:** Before investing in any fund or company, conduct thorough research to ensure they align with your values and have a track record of sustainable and ethical practices. Look for transparency in reporting and adherence to recognized standards.
7. **Long-Term Perspective:** Investing should be approached with a long-term perspective, especially when considering low-risk options. Stay committed to your investment strategy and avoid making impulsive decisions based on short-term market fluctuations.
8. **Financial Education:** Continuously educate yourself about sustainable and ethical investing principles and practices. This will empower you to make informed decisions and stay aligned with your values as your financial situation evolves.

Remember that while investing can help you grow your wealth over time, it's essential to balance potential returns with your risk tolerance and values. Consider consulting with a financial advisor who specializes in sustainable and ethical investing to create a tailored investment plan that aligns with your goals and values.

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<p><i>How does the recommended investment strategy meet the client's investment objectives, considering their personal circumstances, investment term required, knowledge and experience, attitude to risk, capacity to sustain losses and sustainability preferences?</i></p>	<p>The question is partially answered (i.e., the client's actual knowledge and experience are not taken into account, although the system recommends enhancing financial education; but besides this, the question is answered).</p>
<p><i>What measures were taken, post-hoc, to ensure that the advice given meets the client's investment objectives, financial capacity for investment risks, and knowledge understanding of the risks?</i></p>	<p>This was not answered. The tool was not provided by an investment firm. It was mainly designed to return a generic 'investment strategy' rather than personalised investment advice.</p>
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Medium-Risk Investor Persona

Description

I am Morgan, 32 years old, and I have just inherited a substantial amount of financial assets worth \$500,000. I am self-employed and, on average, my monthly income is \$3,000. I am renting an apartment with my partner and paying \$1,250 in rent every month. I have no other incomes or savings and a 2-years old daughter. Her monthly school fee is \$800. So, I am exploring ways of managing the inherited assets effectively, considering that I have a medium risk tolerance.

Gemini's Answer

Congratulations on inheriting a substantial amount of money, Morgan! That's a great opportunity to set yourself and your family up for a secure future. Here are some steps to consider for effectively managing your inherited assets with a medium risk tolerance:

1. Secure Your Financial Footing:

- **Emergency Fund:** With a young child and self-employment, having a safety net is crucial. Aim for 3-6 months of living expenses (around \$18,750 - \$37,500) in a high-yield savings account. This buffer protects you from unexpected costs.
- **Debt Repayment:** If you have any high-interest debt, consider paying it down with some of the inheritance. This frees up future income for other goals.

2. Invest for the Long Term:

- **Investment Time Horizon:** You have a medium risk tolerance and a young child, so consider a long-term investment approach (10+ years). This allows time for the market to recover from any downturns.

3. Diversification is Key:

- **Medium-Risk Asset Allocation:** With a medium risk tolerance, you can explore a mix of asset classes:
 - **40-50% in Stocks:** Invest in a diversified mix of stocks through mutual funds or ETFs. Consider a mix of large-cap and small-cap stocks, balancing growth potential with stability.
 - **30-40% in Bonds:** Invest in a mix of bonds to provide income and stability. Look at investment-grade bonds and consider a mix of maturities to manage interest rate risk.
 - **10-20% in Alternative Investments:** Explore alternative investments like real estate investment trusts (REITs) or commodities for some diversification beyond

stocks and bonds. However, research these options carefully, as they can be complex.

4. Investment Options for Medium Risk Tolerance:

- **Robo-advisors:** These automated investment platforms consider your risk tolerance and create a diversified portfolio based on your goals. They are a good option for beginners and typically have lower fees than traditional financial advisors.
- **Target-Date Funds:** These mutual funds automatically adjust their asset allocation over time, becoming more conservative as you near your retirement age. Choose a target-date fund with a retirement date aligned with your long-term goals.
- **Self-Directed Investing:** If you have some investment knowledge, you can research and build your own diversified portfolio using individual stocks and bonds or ETFs. However, this requires ongoing research and management.

5. Professional Guidance:

- **Financial Advisor:** Consider consulting a fee-based financial advisor specializing in wealth management. They can create a personalized plan based on your specific circumstances, risk tolerance, and long-term goals. They can also help you navigate tax implications and estate planning considerations for your inheritance.

Additional Tips:

- **Don't Rush:** Take your time to research and understand different investment options before making any decisions.
- **Rebalance Regularly:** Review and rebalance your portfolio periodically to maintain your desired asset allocation.
- **Protect Your Assets:** Consider disability insurance to safeguard your income in case you cannot work due to illness or injury.
- **Tax Implications:** Consult a tax advisor to understand any tax implications associated with inheriting assets.

By following these steps and seeking professional guidance if needed, you can effectively manage your inherited assets and build a secure financial future for yourself and your family. Remember, the key is to find a balance between risk and return that aligns with your comfort level and long-term goals.

Explanatory Questions and Assessment

Question	Assessment
<i>What information was used to assess the client's knowledge and experience in the investment field,</i>	Answered (i.e., by first asking the system what information it needed to be able to provide personalised investment advice).

<i>financial situation, investment objectives, and risk tolerance?</i>	
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<i>What measures were taken, post-hoc, to ensure that the advice given meets the client's investment objectives, financial capacity for investment risks, and knowledge understanding of the risks?</i>	This was not answered. The tool was not provided by an investment firm. It was mainly designed to return a generic 'investment strategy' rather than personalised investment advice.
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ChatGPT's Answer

Given your situation and medium risk tolerance, here are some personalized strategies for managing your inherited assets effectively:

1. **Emergency Fund:** Before investing the inherited assets, ensure you have an adequate emergency fund covering at least three to six months of living expenses. This fund should be easily accessible in case of unexpected expenses or emergencies.
2. **Debt Management:** Evaluate any existing debts you may have and prioritize paying off high-interest debts, if any. Since you mentioned no other debts, focus on maintaining a good credit score and managing your expenses efficiently.
3. **Investment Strategy:** With a medium risk tolerance, consider a balanced investment approach that includes a mix of stocks, bonds, and possibly other asset classes such as real estate investment trusts (REITs) or alternative investments. This can help you achieve growth while managing risk.
4. **Education Planning:** Since you have a 2-year-old daughter with monthly school fees of \$800, consider setting aside funds for her education expenses in the future. You may want to explore tax-advantaged college savings plans such as 529 plans or education savings accounts (ESAs).
5. **Retirement Planning:** As a self-employed individual, it's essential to prioritize your retirement savings. Consider opening a retirement account such as a Solo 401(k) or a Simplified Employee Pension (SEP) IRA to save for retirement while potentially benefiting from tax advantages.
6. **Real Estate Consideration:** Given that you're currently renting an apartment, you may want to explore the possibility of using some of the inherited assets for a down payment on a home. However, make sure to carefully assess the affordability and long-term financial implications before making such a decision.
7. **Child's Future Needs:** In addition to education expenses, consider other future needs of your daughter such as healthcare, extracurricular activities, and potential inheritance planning. Setting up a trust or other estate planning tools may be beneficial to ensure her financial security in the future.
8. **Regular Review and Adjustment:** Continuously monitor your investment portfolio and financial plan to ensure they remain aligned with your goals, risk tolerance, and changing financial circumstances. Periodically reassess your investment strategy and make adjustments as needed.

By implementing these strategies and considerations, you can effectively manage your inherited assets, provide for your family's current and future needs, and work towards achieving your financial goals. Consider consulting with a financial advisor to develop a personalized financial plan tailored to your specific situation and objectives.

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High-Risk Investor Persona

Description

My name is Sam, 43 years old, with significant financial assets worth about \$3,000,000 that are currently generating a steady income of \$4,000 per month. I work also as a freelance in the fashion field and I earn, on average, \$5,000 per month. I love traveling and living in luxury. I seek a sophisticated estate planning and wealth management that can quickly improve my lifestyle.

Gemini's Answer

Sounds like you've built a very successful career, Sam! With your significant financial assets and desire for an elevated lifestyle, sophisticated estate planning and wealth management are crucial. Here's how we can approach this:

Enhancing Your Lifestyle:

- **Cash Flow Analysis:** A financial advisor can analyze your current income streams (investment income, freelance work) and expenses to identify areas for optimization. This might involve reducing unnecessary expenses or finding tax-efficient ways to allocate your income for your desired lifestyle.
- **Investment Review:** Review your current investments to ensure they align with your goals. Are they generating enough income to support your desired lifestyle? A wealth manager can suggest adjustments to potentially increase returns while considering your risk tolerance.

Sophisticated Estate Planning and Wealth Management:

- **Wealth Manager or Family Office:** Consider establishing a relationship with a qualified wealth manager or even a family office if your assets are very substantial. They can provide a holistic approach to managing your wealth, including:
 - **Investment Management:** Tailored investment strategies to potentially grow your wealth and support your lifestyle.
 - **Tax Planning:** Strategies to minimize your tax burden and maximize your after-tax income.
 - **Estate Planning:** Ensuring your assets are distributed according to your wishes after your passing away. This could involve trusts, wills, and beneficiary designations.
 - **Risk Management:** Strategies to safeguard your assets from potential risks like lawsuits or economic downturns.
 - **Lifestyle Management:** Assist with high-net-worth services like travel planning, property management, or luxury goods acquisition (if desired).

Additional Considerations:

- **Charitable Giving:** If you're passionate about certain causes, integrate charitable giving strategies into your wealth management plan. Donor-advised funds or charitable trusts can be effective tools.
- **Philanthropic Lifestyle:** Explore foundations or giving circles that combine philanthropy with travel or other luxury experiences.
- **Impact Investing:** Consider investments that generate positive social or environmental impact alongside financial returns.

Finding the Right Professionals:

- Look for experienced advisors with a proven track record in handling complex estates and wealth management for high-net-worth individuals.
- Seek referrals from trusted sources like your accountant, lawyer, or business network.
- Conduct interviews with potential advisors to assess their qualifications, experience, investment philosophy, and fees.

By implementing these steps, you can create a comprehensive wealth management plan that allows you to enjoy your desired lifestyle while safeguarding your assets for the future. Remember, this is an ongoing process. Regular communication and adjustments with your wealth management team are key to navigating your financial future and achieving your long-term goals.

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<i>How does the recommended investment strategy meet the client's investment objectives, considering their personal circumstances, investment term required, knowledge and experience, attitude to risk, capacity to sustain losses and sustainability preferences?</i>	Poorly answered (i.e., the information is only partly relevant, as it focused more on advising to consult a financial advisor than on giving actual investment recommendations.).
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ChatGPT's Answer

Given your significant financial assets and desire for a sophisticated estate planning and wealth management strategy to improve your lifestyle, here are some tailored recommendations:

- 1. Comprehensive Financial Planning:** Work with a team of financial advisors, estate planning attorneys, and tax professionals to develop a comprehensive financial plan tailored to your goals. This plan should encompass wealth management, tax optimization, estate planning, risk management, and retirement planning.
- 2. Asset Allocation and Investment Management:** Develop a diversified investment portfolio that aligns with your risk tolerance, financial goals, and lifestyle preferences. Consider allocating a portion of your assets to growth-oriented investments such as stocks and real estate to maximize returns while managing risk. Additionally, explore alternative investments such as private equity, hedge funds, and venture capital for potential higher returns.
- 3. Tax Optimization Strategies:** Implement tax-efficient strategies to minimize your tax liabilities and maximize after-tax returns. This may include tax-loss harvesting, charitable giving, retirement account contributions, and strategic use of trusts and other tax-advantaged vehicles.
- 4. Estate Planning:** Develop an estate plan that ensures your assets are transferred according to your wishes and minimizes estate taxes and probate costs. Consider setting up trusts such as revocable living trusts, irrevocable trusts, and charitable trusts to protect your assets, provide for your loved ones, and support philanthropic causes.
- 5. Insurance Coverage:** Review your insurance coverage, including life insurance, disability insurance, and liability insurance, to ensure adequate protection for yourself, your family, and your assets. Consider purchasing umbrella insurance to provide additional liability coverage beyond your existing policies.
- 6. Legacy and Philanthropy:** Explore opportunities for philanthropy and legacy planning to support causes that are meaningful to you and leave a lasting impact on society. Consider establishing a donor-advised fund or charitable foundation to facilitate charitable giving and support charitable initiatives in line with your values.
- 7. Lifestyle Management:** Work with a lifestyle manager or concierge service to enhance your lifestyle and streamline your day-to-day activities. This may include travel planning, luxury experiences, event coordination, and personal assistance services tailored to your preferences and needs.

8. **Regular Review and Adjustment:** Continuously monitor your financial plan and investment portfolio, and be prepared to adjust your strategies as your goals, preferences, and market conditions change. Regular reviews with your financial advisors and estate planning professionals can help ensure your plan remains aligned with your evolving needs and objectives.

By implementing these sophisticated estate planning and wealth management strategies, you can enhance your lifestyle, protect your assets, and leave a lasting legacy for future generations. Consider working with a team of experienced professionals who can provide personalized advice and guidance tailored to your unique financial situation and goals.

Explanatory Questions and Assessment

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